

PISA Results, 2000-2015

Reading Literacy, Mathematical Literacy, Science Literacy

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Data by Country/Region All Assessment Cycles, All Countries

Main Sources:

Reading, 2000-2015: Table I.4.4a in <http://dx.doi.org/10.1787/888933433195>
Mathematics, 2003-2015: Table I.5.4a in <http://dx.doi.org/10.1787/888933433203>
Science, 2006-2015: Table I.2.4a in <http://dx.doi.org/10.1787/888933433171>

Table 1: PISA Scores in Reading Literacy, Mathematical Literacy, and Science Literacy (with SE, “standard errors”), 2000-2015

Note: Values in unfilled bars are not comparable.

Country/Region	OECD/ Partner	Year	All Cycles	Reading Literacy	Reading Literacy SE	Mathematical Literacy	Mathematical Literacy SE	Science Literacy	Science Literacy SE			
Albania	Partner	2000	No		349	3.3		381	3.1		376	2.9
Albania	Partner	2003	No									
Albania	Partner	2006	No									
Albania	Partner	2009	No		385	4.0		377	4.0		391	3.9
Albania	Partner	2012	No		394	3.2		394	2.0		397	2.4
Albania	Partner	2015	No		405	4.1		413	3.4		427	3.3
Algeria	Partner	2000	No									
Algeria	Partner	2003	No									
Algeria	Partner	2006	No									
Algeria	Partner	2009	No									
Algeria	Partner	2012	No									
Algeria	Partner	2015	No		350	3.0		360	3.0		376	2.6
Argentina	Partner	2000	No		418	9.9		388	9.4		396	8.6
Argentina	Partner	2003	No									
Argentina	Partner	2006	No		374	7.2		381	6.2		391	6.1
Argentina	Partner	2009	No		398	4.6		388	4.1		401	4.6
Argentina	Partner	2012	No		396	3.7		388	3.5		406	3.9
Argentina	Partner	2015	No		425	3.2		409	3.1		432	2.9
Australia	OECD	2000	Yes		528	3.5		533	3.5		528	3.5
Australia	OECD	2003	Yes		525	2.1		524	2.1		525	2.1
Australia	OECD	2006	Yes		513	2.1		520	2.2		527	2.3
Australia	OECD	2009	Yes		515	2.3		514	2.5		527	2.5
Australia	OECD	2012	Yes		512	1.6		504	1.6		521	1.8
Australia	OECD	2015	Yes		503	1.7		494	1.6		510	1.5
Austria	OECD	2000	No		492	2.7		515	2.5		519	2.6
Austria	OECD	2003	No		491	3.8		506	3.3		491	3.4
Austria	OECD	2006	No		490	4.1		505	3.7		511	3.9
Austria	OECD	2009	No									
Austria	OECD	2012	No		490	2.8		506	2.7		506	2.7
Austria	OECD	2015	No		485	2.8		497	2.9		495	2.4
Azerbaijan	Partner	2000	No									
Azerbaijan	Partner	2003	No									
Azerbaijan	Partner	2006	No		353	3.1		476	2.3		382	2.8
Azerbaijan	Partner	2009	No		362	3.3		432	2.8		373	3.1
Azerbaijan	Partner	2012	No									
Azerbaijan	Partner	2015	No									
B-S-J-G (China)	Partner	2000	No									
B-S-J-G (China)	Partner	2003	No									
B-S-J-G (China)	Partner	2006	No									
B-S-J-G (China)	Partner	2009	No									
B-S-J-G (China)	Partner	2012	No									
B-S-J-G (China)	Partner	2015	No		494	5.1		531	4.9		518	4.6
Belgium	OECD	2000	Yes		507	3.6		520	3.9		496	4.3
Belgium	OECD	2003	Yes		507	2.6		529	2.3		509	2.5
Belgium	OECD	2006	Yes		501	3.0		520	3.0		510	2.5
Belgium	OECD	2009	Yes		506	2.3		515	2.3		507	2.5
Belgium	OECD	2012	Yes		509	2.3		515	2.1		505	2.2
Belgium	OECD	2015	Yes		499	2.4		507	2.4		502	2.3
Brazil	Partner	2000	Yes		396	3.1		334	3.7		375	3.3
Brazil	Partner	2003	Yes		403	4.6		356	4.8		390	4.3
Brazil	Partner	2006	Yes		393	3.7		370	2.9		390	2.8
Brazil	Partner	2009	Yes		412	2.7		386	2.4		405	2.4
Brazil	Partner	2012	Yes		407	2.0		389	1.9		402	2.1
Brazil	Partner	2015	Yes		407	2.8		377	2.9		401	2.3
Bulgaria	Partner	2000	No		430	4.9		430	5.7		448	4.6
Bulgaria	Partner	2003	No									
Bulgaria	Partner	2006	No		402	6.9		413	6.1		434	6.1
Bulgaria	Partner	2009	No		429	6.7		428	5.9		439	5.9
Bulgaria	Partner	2012	No		436	6.0		439	4.0		446	4.8
Bulgaria	Partner	2015	No		432	5.0		441	4.0		446	4.4
CABA (Argentina)	Partner	2000	No									
CABA (Argentina)	Partner	2003	No									
CABA (Argentina)	Partner	2006	No									
CABA (Argentina)	Partner	2009	No									
CABA (Argentina)	Partner	2012	No		429	9.0		418	7.3		425	8.6
CABA (Argentina)	Partner	2015	No		475	7.2		456	6.9		475	6.3
Canada	OECD	2000	Yes		534	1.6		533	1.4		529	1.6
Canada	OECD	2003	Yes		528	1.7		532	1.8		519	2.0
Canada	OECD	2006	Yes		527	2.4		527	2.0		534	2.0
Canada	OECD	2009	Yes		524	1.5		527	1.6		529	1.6
Canada	OECD	2012	Yes		523	1.9		518	1.8		525	1.9
Canada	OECD	2015	Yes		527	2.3		516	2.3		528	2.1
Chile	Partner	2000	No		410	3.6		384	3.7		415	3.4
Chile	Partner	2003	No									
Chile	Partner	2006	No		442	5.0		411	4.6		438	4.3
Chile	Partner	2009	No		449	3.1		421	3.1		447	2.9
Chile	OECD	2012	No		441	2.9		423	3.1		445	2.9
Chile	OECD	2015	No		459	2.6		423	2.5		447	2.4

Table 1: PISA Scores in Reading Literacy, Mathematical Literacy, and Science Literacy (with SE, “standard errors”), 2000-2015
(cont.)

Note: Values in unfilled bars are not comparable.

Country/Region	OECD/ Partner	Year	All Cycles	Reading Literacy	Reading Literacy SE	Mathematical Literacy	Mathematical Literacy SE	Science Literacy	Science Literacy SE
Chinese Taipei	Partner	2000	No						
Chinese Taipei	Partner	2003	No						
Chinese Taipei	Partner	2006	No	■	496	3.4	■	532	3.6
Chinese Taipei	Partner	2009	No	■	495	2.6	■	520	2.6
Chinese Taipei	Partner	2012	No	■	523	3.0	■	523	2.3
Chinese Taipei	Partner	2015	No	■	497	2.5	■	532	2.7
Colombia	Partner	2000	No						
Colombia	Partner	2003	No						
Colombia	Partner	2006	No	■	385	5.1	■	388	3.4
Colombia	Partner	2009	No	■	413	3.7	■	402	3.6
Colombia	Partner	2012	No	■	403	3.4	■	399	3.1
Colombia	Partner	2015	No	■	425	2.9	■	416	2.4
Costa Rica	Partner	2000	No						
Costa Rica	Partner	2003	No						
Costa Rica	Partner	2006	No						
Costa Rica	Partner	2009	No	■	443	3.2	■	430	2.8
Costa Rica	Partner	2012	No	■	441	3.5	■	429	2.9
Costa Rica	Partner	2015	No	■	427	2.6	■	420	2.1
Croatia	Partner	2000	No						
Croatia	Partner	2003	No						
Croatia	Partner	2006	No	■	477	2.8	■	493	2.4
Croatia	Partner	2009	No	■	476	2.9	■	486	2.8
Croatia	Partner	2012	No	■	485	3.3	■	491	3.1
Croatia	Partner	2015	No	■	487	2.7	■	475	2.5
Cyprus	Partner	2000	No						
Cyprus	Partner	2003	No						
Cyprus	Partner	2006	No						
Cyprus	Partner	2009	No						
Cyprus	Partner	2012	No	■	449	1.2	■	438	1.2
Cyprus	Partner	2015	No	■	443	1.7	■	433	1.4
Czech Republic	OECD	2000	Yes	■	492	2.4	■	511	2.4
Czech Republic	OECD	2003	Yes	■	489	3.5	■	523	3.4
Czech Republic	OECD	2006	Yes	■	483	4.2	■	513	3.5
Czech Republic	OECD	2009	Yes	■	478	2.9	■	500	3.0
Czech Republic	OECD	2012	Yes	■	493	2.9	■	508	3.0
Czech Republic	OECD	2015	Yes	■	487	2.6	■	493	2.3
Denmark	OECD	2000	Yes	■	497	2.4	■	481	2.8
Denmark	OECD	2003	Yes	■	492	2.8	■	475	3.0
Denmark	OECD	2006	Yes	■	494	3.2	■	496	3.1
Denmark	OECD	2009	Yes	■	495	2.1	■	499	2.5
Denmark	OECD	2012	Yes	■	496	2.6	■	498	2.7
Denmark	OECD	2015	Yes	■	500	2.5	■	502	2.4
Dominican Republic	Partner	2000	No						
Dominican Republic	Partner	2003	No						
Dominican Republic	Partner	2006	No						
Dominican Republic	Partner	2009	No						
Dominican Republic	Partner	2012	No						
Dominican Republic	Partner	2015	No	■	358	3.1	■	332	2.6
Dubai	Partner	2000	No						
Dubai	Partner	2003	No						
Dubai	Partner	2006	No						
Dubai	Partner	2009	No	■	459	1.1	■	466	1.2
Dubai	Partner	2012	No						
Dubai	Partner	2015	No						
Estonia	OECD	2000	No						
Estonia	OECD	2003	No						
Estonia	OECD	2006	No	■	501	2.9	■	531	2.5
Estonia	OECD	2009	No	■	501	2.6	■	528	2.7
Estonia	OECD	2012	No	■	516	2.0	■	541	1.9
Estonia	OECD	2015	No	■	519	2.2	■	534	2.1
Finland	OECD	2000	Yes	■	546	2.6	■	538	2.5
Finland	OECD	2003	Yes	■	543	1.6	■	548	1.9
Finland	OECD	2006	Yes	■	547	2.1	■	563	2.0
Finland	OECD	2009	Yes	■	536	2.3	■	554	2.3
Finland	OECD	2012	Yes	■	524	2.4	■	545	2.2
Finland	OECD	2015	Yes	■	526	2.5	■	531	2.4
France	OECD	2000	Yes	■	505	2.7	■	500	3.2
France	OECD	2003	Yes	■	496	2.7	■	511	3.0
France	OECD	2006	Yes	■	488	4.1	■	495	3.4
France	OECD	2009	Yes	■	496	3.4	■	498	3.6
France	OECD	2012	Yes	■	505	2.8	■	499	2.6
France	OECD	2015	Yes	■	499	2.5	■	495	2.1
FYROM (Macedonia)	Partner	2000	No	■	373	1.9	■	401	2.1
FYROM (Macedonia)	Partner	2003	No						
FYROM (Macedonia)	Partner	2006	No						
FYROM (Macedonia)	Partner	2009	No						
FYROM (Macedonia)	Partner	2012	No						
FYROM (Macedonia)	Partner	2015	No	■	352	1.4	■	384	1.2

Table 1: PISA Scores in Reading Literacy, Mathematical Literacy, and Science Literacy (with SE, “standard errors”), 2000-2015
(cont.)

Note: Values in unfilled bars are not comparable.

Country/Region	OECD/ Partner	Year	All Cycles	Reading Literacy	Reading Literacy SE	Mathematical Literacy	Mathematical Literacy SE	Science Literacy	Science Literacy SE
Georgia	Partner	2000	No						
Georgia	Partner	2003	No						
Georgia	Partner	2006	No						
Georgia	Partner	2009	No	■	374	2.9	■	373	2.9
Georgia	Partner	2012	No						
Georgia	Partner	2015	No	■	401	3.0	■	411	2.4
Germany	OECD	2000	Yes	■	484	2.5	■	487	2.4
Germany	OECD	2003	Yes	■	491	3.4	■	502	3.6
Germany	OECD	2006	Yes	■	495	4.4	■	516	3.8
Germany	OECD	2009	Yes	■	497	2.7	■	520	2.8
Germany	OECD	2012	Yes	■	508	2.8	■	524	3.0
Germany	OECD	2015	Yes	■	509	3.0	■	509	2.7
Greece	OECD	2000	Yes	■	474	5.0	■	461	4.9
Greece	OECD	2003	Yes	■	472	4.1	■	481	3.8
Greece	OECD	2006	Yes	■	460	4.0	■	473	3.2
Greece	OECD	2009	Yes	■	483	4.3	■	470	4.0
Greece	OECD	2012	Yes	■	477	3.3	■	467	3.1
Greece	OECD	2015	Yes	■	467	4.3	■	455	3.9
Hong Kong (China)	Partner	2000	Yes	■	525	2.9	■	541	3.0
Hong Kong (China)	Partner	2003	Yes	■	510	3.7	■	539	4.3
Hong Kong (China)	Partner	2006	Yes	■	536	2.4	■	542	2.5
Hong Kong (China)	Partner	2009	Yes	■	533	2.1	■	549	2.8
Hong Kong (China)	Partner	2012	Yes	■	545	2.8	■	555	2.6
Hong Kong (China)	Partner	2015	Yes	■	527	2.7	■	523	2.5
Hungary	OECD	2000	Yes	■	480	4.0	■	496	4.2
Hungary	OECD	2003	Yes	■	482	2.5	■	503	2.8
Hungary	OECD	2006	Yes	■	482	3.3	■	504	2.7
Hungary	OECD	2009	Yes	■	494	3.2	■	503	3.1
Hungary	OECD	2012	Yes	■	488	3.2	■	494	2.9
Hungary	OECD	2015	Yes	■	470	2.7	■	477	2.4
Iceland	OECD	2000	Yes	■	507	1.5	■	496	2.2
Iceland	OECD	2003	Yes	■	492	1.6	■	495	1.5
Iceland	OECD	2006	Yes	■	484	1.9	■	491	1.6
Iceland	OECD	2009	Yes	■	500	1.4	■	496	1.4
Iceland	OECD	2012	Yes	■	483	1.8	■	478	2.1
Iceland	OECD	2015	Yes	■	482	2.0	■	473	1.7
India - Himachal Pradesh	OECD	2000	No						
India - Himachal Pradesh	OECD	2003	No						
India - Himachal Pradesh	OECD	2006	No						
India - Himachal Pradesh	OECD	2009	No	■	317	4.0	■	325	4.2
India - Himachal Pradesh	OECD	2012	No						
India - Himachal Pradesh	OECD	2015	No						
India - Tamil Nadu	OECD	2000	No						
India - Tamil Nadu	OECD	2003	No						
India - Tamil Nadu	OECD	2006	No						
India - Tamil Nadu	OECD	2009	No	■	337	5.5	■	348	4.2
India - Tamil Nadu	OECD	2012	No						
India - Tamil Nadu	OECD	2015	No						
Indonesia	Partner	2000	Yes	■	371	4.0	■	393	3.9
Indonesia	Partner	2003	Yes	■	382	3.4	■	395	3.2
Indonesia	Partner	2006	Yes	■	393	5.9	■	393	5.7
Indonesia	Partner	2009	Yes	■	402	3.7	■	383	3.8
Indonesia	Partner	2012	Yes	■	396	4.2	■	382	3.8
Indonesia	Partner	2015	Yes	■	397	2.9	■	403	2.6
Ireland	OECD	2000	Yes	■	527	3.2	■	513	3.2
Ireland	OECD	2003	Yes	■	515	2.6	■	505	2.7
Ireland	OECD	2006	Yes	■	517	3.5	■	508	3.2
Ireland	OECD	2009	Yes	■	496	3.0	■	508	3.3
Ireland	OECD	2012	Yes	■	523	2.6	■	522	2.5
Ireland	OECD	2015	Yes	■	521	2.5	■	503	2.4
Israel	Partner	2000	No	■	452	8.5	■	434	9.0
Israel	Partner	2003	No						
Israel	Partner	2006	No	■	439	4.6	■	454	3.7
Israel	Partner	2009	No	■	474	3.6	■	455	3.1
Israel	OECD	2012	No	■	486	5.0	■	470	5.0
Israel	OECD	2015	No	■	479	3.8	■	467	3.4
Italy	OECD	2000	Yes	■	487	2.9	■	478	3.1
Italy	OECD	2003	Yes	■	476	3.0	■	486	3.1
Italy	OECD	2006	Yes	■	469	2.4	■	475	2.0
Italy	OECD	2009	Yes	■	486	1.6	■	489	1.8
Italy	OECD	2012	Yes	■	490	2.0	■	494	1.9
Italy	OECD	2015	Yes	■	485	2.7	■	481	2.5
Japan	OECD	2000	Yes	■	522	5.2	■	550	5.5
Japan	OECD	2003	Yes	■	498	3.9	■	548	4.1
Japan	OECD	2006	Yes	■	498	3.6	■	531	3.4
Japan	OECD	2009	Yes	■	520	3.5	■	539	3.4
Japan	OECD	2012	Yes	■	538	3.7	■	547	3.6
Japan	OECD	2015	Yes	■	516	3.2	■	538	3.0

Table 1: PISA Scores in Reading Literacy, Mathematical Literacy, and Science Literacy (with SE, “standard errors”), 2000-2015
(cont.)

Note: Values in unfilled bars are not comparable.

Country/Region	OECD/ Partner	Year	All Cycles	Reading Literacy	Reading Literacy SE	Mathematical Literacy	Mathematical Literacy SE	Science Literacy	Science Literacy SE
Jordan	Partner	2000	No						
Jordan	Partner	2003	No						
Jordan	Partner	2006	No	■	401	3.3	■	422	2.8
Jordan	Partner	2009	No	■	405	3.3	■	415	3.5
Jordan	Partner	2012	No	■	399	3.6	■	409	3.1
Jordan	Partner	2015	No	■	408	2.9	■	409	2.7
Kazakhstan	Partner	2000	No						
Kazakhstan	Partner	2003	No						
Kazakhstan	Partner	2006	No						
Kazakhstan	Partner	2009	No	■	390	3.1	■	400	3.1
Kazakhstan	Partner	2012	No	■	393	2.7	■	425	3.0
Kazakhstan	Partner	2015	No	■	427	3.4	■	456	3.7
Korea	OECD	2000	Yes	■	525	2.4	■	552	2.7
Korea	OECD	2003	Yes	■	534	3.1	■	538	3.5
Korea	OECD	2006	Yes	■	556	3.8	■	522	3.4
Korea	OECD	2009	Yes	■	539	3.5	■	538	3.4
Korea	OECD	2012	Yes	■	536	3.9	■	538	3.7
Korea	OECD	2015	Yes	■	517	3.5	■	516	3.1
Kosovo	Partner	2000	No						
Kosovo	Partner	2003	No						
Kosovo	Partner	2006	No						
Kosovo	Partner	2009	No						
Kosovo	Partner	2012	No						
Kosovo	Partner	2015	No	■	347	1.6	■	378	1.7
Kyrgyzstan	Partner	2000	No						
Kyrgyzstan	Partner	2003	No						
Kyrgyzstan	Partner	2006	No	■	285	3.5	■	322	2.9
Kyrgyzstan	Partner	2009	No	■	314	3.2	■	330	2.9
Kyrgyzstan	Partner	2012	No						
Kyrgyzstan	Partner	2015	No						
Latvia	Partner	2000	Yes	■	458	5.3	■	460	5.6
Latvia	Partner	2003	Yes	■	491	3.7	■	489	3.9
Latvia	Partner	2006	Yes	■	479	3.7	■	490	3.0
Latvia	Partner	2009	Yes	■	484	3.0	■	494	3.1
Latvia	Partner	2012	Yes	■	489	2.4	■	502	2.8
Latvia	Partner	2015	Yes	■	488	1.8	■	490	1.6
Lebanon	Partner	2000	No						
Lebanon	Partner	2003	No						
Lebanon	Partner	2006	No						
Lebanon	Partner	2009	No						
Lebanon	Partner	2012	No						
Lebanon	Partner	2015	No	■	347	4.4	■	386	3.4
Liechtenstein	Partner	2000	No	■	483	4.1	■	476	7.1
Liechtenstein	Partner	2003	No	■	525	3.6	■	525	4.3
Liechtenstein	Partner	2006	No	■	510	3.9	■	522	4.1
Liechtenstein	Partner	2009	No	■	499	2.8	■	520	3.4
Liechtenstein	Partner	2012	No	■	516	4.1	■	525	3.5
Liechtenstein	Partner	2015	No						
Lithuania	Partner	2000	No						
Lithuania	Partner	2003	No						
Lithuania	Partner	2006	No	■	470	3.0	■	488	2.8
Lithuania	Partner	2009	No	■	468	2.4	■	491	2.9
Lithuania	Partner	2012	No	■	477	2.5	■	496	2.6
Lithuania	Partner	2015	No	■	472	2.7	■	475	2.7
Luxembourg	OECD	2000	Yes	■	441	1.6	■	443	2.3
Luxembourg	OECD	2003	Yes	■	479	1.5	■	483	1.5
Luxembourg	OECD	2006	Yes	■	479	1.3	■	486	1.1
Luxembourg	OECD	2009	Yes	■	472	1.3	■	484	1.2
Luxembourg	OECD	2012	Yes	■	488	1.5	■	491	1.3
Luxembourg	OECD	2015	Yes	■	481	1.4	■	483	1.1
Macao (China)	Partner	2000	No						
Macao (China)	Partner	2003	No	■	498	2.2	■	525	3.0
Macao (China)	Partner	2006	No	■	492	1.1	■	511	1.1
Macao (China)	Partner	2009	No	■	487	0.9	■	511	1.0
Macao (China)	Partner	2012	No	■	509	0.9	■	521	0.8
Macao (China)	Partner	2015	No	■	509	1.3	■	529	1.1
Malaysia	Partner	2000	No						
Malaysia	Partner	2003	No						
Malaysia	Partner	2006	No						
Malaysia	Partner	2009	No	■	414	2.9	■	422	2.7
Malaysia	Partner	2012	No	■	398	3.3	■	420	3.0
Malaysia	Partner	2015	No	■	431	3.5	■	443	3.0
Malta	Partner	2000	No						
Malta	Partner	2003	No						
Malta	Partner	2006	No						
Malta	Partner	2009	No	■	442	1.6	■	461	1.7
Malta	Partner	2012	No						
Malta	Partner	2015	No	■	447	1.8	■	465	1.6

Table 1: PISA Scores in Reading Literacy, Mathematical Literacy, and Science Literacy (with SE, “standard errors”), 2000-2015
(cont.)

Note: Values in unfilled bars are not comparable.

Country/Region	OECD/ Partner	Year	All Cycles	Reading Literacy	Reading Literacy SE	Mathematical Literacy	Mathematical Literacy SE	Science Literacy	Science Literacy SE			
Mauritius	Partner	2000	No									
Mauritius	Partner	2003	No									
Mauritius	Partner	2006	No									
Mauritius	Partner	2009	No		407	1.1		420	1.0		417	1.1
Mauritius	Partner	2012	No									
Mauritius	Partner	2015	No									
Mexico	OECD	2000	Yes		422	3.3		387	3.4		422	3.2
Mexico	OECD	2003	Yes		400	4.1		385	3.6		405	3.5
Mexico	OECD	2006	Yes		410	3.1		406	2.9		410	2.7
Mexico	OECD	2009	Yes		425	2.0		419	1.8		416	1.8
Mexico	OECD	2012	Yes		424	1.5		413	1.4		415	1.3
Mexico	OECD	2015	Yes		423	2.6		408	2.2		416	2.1
Moldova	Partner	2000	No									
Moldova	Partner	2003	No									
Moldova	Partner	2006	No									
Moldova	Partner	2009	No		388	2.8		397	3.1		413	3.0
Moldova	Partner	2012	No									
Moldova	Partner	2015	No		416	2.5		420	2.5		428	2.0
Montenegro	Partner	2000	No									
Montenegro	Partner	2003	No									
Montenegro	Partner	2006	No		392	1.2		399	1.4		412	1.1
Montenegro	Partner	2009	No		408	1.7		403	2.0		401	2.0
Montenegro	Partner	2012	No		422	1.2		410	1.1		410	1.1
Montenegro	Partner	2015	No		427	1.6		418	1.5		411	1.0
Netherlands	OECD	2000	No									
Netherlands	OECD	2003	No		513	2.9		538	3.1		524	3.1
Netherlands	OECD	2006	No		507	2.9		531	2.6		525	2.7
Netherlands	OECD	2009	No		508	5.1		526	4.7		522	5.4
Netherlands	OECD	2012	No		511	3.5		523	3.5		522	3.5
Netherlands	OECD	2015	No		503	2.4		512	2.2		509	2.3
New Zealand	OECD	2000	Yes		529	2.8		537	3.1		528	2.4
New Zealand	OECD	2003	Yes		522	2.5		523	2.3		521	2.4
New Zealand	OECD	2006	Yes		521	3.0		522	2.4		530	2.7
New Zealand	OECD	2009	Yes		521	2.4		519	2.3		532	2.6
New Zealand	OECD	2012	Yes		512	2.4		500	2.2		516	2.1
New Zealand	OECD	2015	Yes		509	2.4		495	2.3		513	2.4
Norway	OECD	2000	Yes		505	2.8		499	2.8		500	2.8
Norway	OECD	2003	Yes		500	2.8		495	2.4		484	2.9
Norway	OECD	2006	Yes		484	3.2		490	2.6		487	3.1
Norway	OECD	2009	Yes		503	2.6		498	2.4		500	2.6
Norway	OECD	2012	Yes		504	3.2		489	2.7		495	3.1
Norway	OECD	2015	Yes		513	2.5		502	2.2		498	2.3
OECD average-24		2000			501	0.7						
OECD average-24		2003			497	0.6						
OECD average-24		2006			495	0.7						
OECD average-24		2009			499	0.6						
OECD average-24		2012			501	0.6						
OECD average-24		2015			498	0.6						
OECD average-28		2000			496	0.7						
OECD average-28		2003										
OECD average-28		2006										
OECD average-28		2009										
OECD average-28		2012			498	0.6						
OECD average-28		2015			495	0.5						
OECD average-30		2000										
OECD average-30		2003			494	0.6		499	0.6			
OECD average-30		2006						497	0.5			
OECD average-30		2009										
OECD average-30		2012			498	0.5		496	0.5			
OECD average-30		2015			493	0.5		491	0.5			
OECD average-34		2000										
OECD average-34		2003										
OECD average-34		2006						494	0.5		498	0.5
OECD average-34		2009			494	0.5		495	0.5		501	0.5
OECD average-34		2012			497	0.5		494	0.5		501	0.5
OECD average-34		2015			493	0.5		490	0.4		493	0.4
OECD average-34-R		2000										
OECD average-34-R		2003										
OECD average-34-R		2006			489	0.6						
OECD average-34-R		2009										
OECD average-34-R		2012			496	0.5						
OECD average-34-R		2015			493	0.5						
OECD average-35		2000										
OECD average-35		2003										
OECD average-35		2006						494	0.5		498	0.5
OECD average-35		2009										
OECD average-35		2012			496	0.5		494	0.5		501	0.5
OECD average-35		2015			493	0.5		490	0.4		493	0.4

Table 1: PISA Scores in Reading Literacy, Mathematical Literacy, and Science Literacy (with SE, “standard errors”), 2000-2015
(cont.)

Note: Values in unfilled bars are not comparable.

Country/Region	OECD/ Partner	Year	All Cycles	Reading Literacy	Reading Literacy SE	Mathematical Literacy	Mathematical Literacy SE	Science Literacy	Science Literacy SE
Panama	Partner	2000	No						
Panama	Partner	2003	No						
Panama	Partner	2006	No						
Panama	Partner	2009	No	■	371	6.5	■	376	5.7
Panama	Partner	2012	No						
Panama	Partner	2015	No						
Peru	Partner	2000	No	■	327	4.4	■	333	4.0
Peru	Partner	2003	No						
Peru	Partner	2006	No						
Peru	Partner	2009	No	■	370	4.0	■	369	3.5
Peru	Partner	2012	No	■	384	4.3	■	373	3.6
Peru	Partner	2015	No	■	398	2.9	■	397	2.4
Poland	OECD	2000	Yes	■	479	4.5	■	483	5.1
Poland	OECD	2003	Yes	■	497	2.9	■	498	2.9
Poland	OECD	2006	Yes	■	508	2.8	■	498	2.3
Poland	OECD	2009	Yes	■	500	2.6	■	508	2.4
Poland	OECD	2012	Yes	■	518	3.1	■	526	3.1
Poland	OECD	2015	Yes	■	506	2.5	■	501	2.5
Portugal	OECD	2000	Yes	■	470	4.5	■	459	4.0
Portugal	OECD	2003	Yes	■	478	3.7	■	468	3.5
Portugal	OECD	2006	Yes	■	472	3.6	■	474	3.0
Portugal	OECD	2009	Yes	■	489	3.1	■	493	2.9
Portugal	OECD	2012	Yes	■	488	3.8	■	489	3.7
Portugal	OECD	2015	Yes	■	498	2.7	■	501	2.4
Qatar	Partner	2000	No						
Qatar	Partner	2003	No						
Qatar	Partner	2006	No	■	312	1.2	■	349	0.9
Qatar	Partner	2009	No	■	372	0.8	■	379	0.9
Qatar	Partner	2012	No	■	388	0.8	■	384	0.7
Qatar	Partner	2015	No	■	402	1.0	■	418	1.0
Romania	Partner	2000	No	■	428	3.5			
Romania	Partner	2003	No						
Romania	Partner	2006	No	■	396	4.7	■	418	4.2
Romania	Partner	2009	No	■	424	4.1	■	428	3.4
Romania	Partner	2012	No	■	438	4.0	■	439	3.3
Romania	Partner	2015	No	■	434	4.1	■	435	3.2
Russia	Partner	2000	Yes	■	462	4.2	■	460	4.7
Russia	Partner	2003	Yes	■	442	3.9	■	489	4.1
Russia	Partner	2006	Yes	■	440	4.3	■	479	3.7
Russia	Partner	2009	Yes	■	459	3.3	■	478	3.3
Russia	Partner	2012	Yes	■	475	3.0	■	486	2.9
Russia	Partner	2015	Yes	■	495	3.1	■	487	2.9
Serbia	Partner	2000	No						
Serbia	Partner	2003	No	■	412	3.6	■	436	3.5
Serbia	Partner	2006	No	■	401	3.5	■	436	3.0
Serbia	Partner	2009	No	■	442	2.4	■	443	2.4
Serbia	Partner	2012	No						
Serbia	Partner	2015	No						
Shanghai (China)	Partner	2000	No						
Shanghai (China)	Partner	2003	No						
Shanghai (China)	Partner	2006	No						
Shanghai (China)	Partner	2009	No	■	556	2.4	■	575	2.3
Shanghai (China)	Partner	2012	No	■	570	2.9	■	580	3.0
Shanghai (China)	Partner	2015	No						
Singapore	Partner	2000	No						
Singapore	Partner	2003	No						
Singapore	Partner	2006	No						
Singapore	Partner	2009	No	■	526	1.1	■	542	1.4
Singapore	Partner	2012	No	■	542	1.4	■	551	1.5
Singapore	Partner	2015	No	■	535	1.6	■	556	1.2
Slovak Republic	OECD	2000	No						
Slovak Republic	OECD	2003	No	■	469	3.1	■	495	3.7
Slovak Republic	OECD	2006	No	■	466	3.1	■	488	2.6
Slovak Republic	OECD	2009	No	■	477	2.5	■	490	3.0
Slovak Republic	OECD	2012	No	■	463	4.2	■	471	3.6
Slovak Republic	OECD	2015	No	■	453	2.8	■	461	2.6
Slovenia	Partner	2000	No						
Slovenia	Partner	2003	No						
Slovenia	Partner	2006	No	■	494	1.0	■	519	1.1
Slovenia	Partner	2009	No	■	483	1.0	■	512	1.1
Slovenia	OECD	2012	No	■	481	1.2	■	514	1.3
Slovenia	OECD	2015	No	■	505	1.5	■	513	1.3
Spain	OECD	2000	Yes	■	493	2.7	■	491	3.0
Spain	OECD	2003	Yes	■	481	2.6	■	487	2.6
Spain	OECD	2006	Yes	■	461	2.2	■	488	2.6
Spain	OECD	2009	Yes	■	481	2.0	■	488	2.1
Spain	OECD	2012	Yes	■	488	1.9	■	496	1.8
Spain	OECD	2015	Yes	■	496	2.4	■	493	2.1

Table 1: PISA Scores in Reading Literacy, Mathematical Literacy, and Science Literacy (with SE, “standard errors”), 2000-2015
(cont.)

Note: Values in unfilled bars are not comparable.

Country/Region	OECD/ Partner	Year	All Cycles	Reading Literacy	Reading Literacy SE	Mathematical Literacy	Mathematical Literacy SE	Science Literacy	Science Literacy SE			
Sweden	OECD	2000	Yes		516	2.2		510	2.5		512	2.5
Sweden	OECD	2003	Yes		514	2.4		509	2.6		506	2.7
Sweden	OECD	2006	Yes		507	3.4		502	2.4		503	2.4
Sweden	OECD	2009	Yes		497	2.9		494	2.9		495	2.7
Sweden	OECD	2012	Yes		483	3.0		478	2.3		485	3.0
Sweden	OECD	2015	Yes		500	3.5		494	3.2		493	3.6
Switzerland	OECD	2000	Yes		494	4.2		529	4.4		496	4.4
Switzerland	OECD	2003	Yes		499	3.3		527	3.4		513	3.7
Switzerland	OECD	2006	Yes		499	3.1		530	3.2		512	3.2
Switzerland	OECD	2009	Yes		501	2.4		534	3.3		517	2.8
Switzerland	OECD	2012	Yes		509	2.6		531	3.0		515	2.7
Switzerland	OECD	2015	Yes		492	3.0		521	2.9		506	2.9
Thailand	Partner	2000	Yes		431	3.2		432	3.6		436	3.1
Thailand	Partner	2003	Yes		420	2.8		417	3.0		429	2.7
Thailand	Partner	2006	Yes		417	2.6		417	2.3		421	2.1
Thailand	Partner	2009	Yes		421	2.6		419	3.2		425	3.0
Thailand	Partner	2012	Yes		441	3.1		427	3.4		444	2.9
Thailand	Partner	2015	Yes		409	3.3		415	3.0		421	2.8
Trinidad and Tobago	Partner	2000	No									
Trinidad and Tobago	Partner	2003	No									
Trinidad and Tobago	Partner	2006	No									
Trinidad and Tobago	Partner	2009	No		416	1.2		414	1.3		410	1.2
Trinidad and Tobago	Partner	2012	No									
Trinidad and Tobago	Partner	2015	No		427	1.5		417	1.4		425	1.4
Tunisia	Partner	2000	No									
Tunisia	Partner	2003	No		375	2.8		359	2.5		385	2.6
Tunisia	Partner	2006	No		380	4.0		365	4.0		386	3.0
Tunisia	Partner	2009	No		404	2.9		371	3.0		401	2.7
Tunisia	Partner	2012	No		404	4.5		388	3.9		398	3.5
Tunisia	Partner	2015	No		361	3.1		367	3.0		386	2.1
Turkey	OECD	2000	No									
Turkey	OECD	2003	No		441	5.8		423	6.7		434	5.9
Turkey	OECD	2006	No		447	4.2		424	4.9		424	3.8
Turkey	OECD	2009	No		464	3.5		445	4.4		454	3.6
Turkey	OECD	2012	No		475	4.2		448	4.8		463	3.9
Turkey	OECD	2015	No		428	4.0		420	4.1		425	3.9
United Arab Emirates	Partner	2000	No									
United Arab Emirates	Partner	2003	No									
United Arab Emirates	Partner	2006	No									
United Arab Emirates	Partner	2009	No									
United Arab Emirates	Partner	2012	No		442	2.5		434	2.4		448	2.8
United Arab Emirates	Partner	2015	No		434	2.9		427	2.4		437	2.4
United Kingdom	OECD	2000	No		523	2.6		529	2.5		532	2.7
United Kingdom	OECD	2003	No									
United Kingdom	OECD	2006	No		495	2.3		495	2.1		515	2.3
United Kingdom	OECD	2009	No		494	2.3		492	2.4		514	2.5
United Kingdom	OECD	2012	No		499	3.5		494	3.3		514	3.4
United Kingdom	OECD	2015	No		498	2.8		492	2.5		509	2.6
United States	OECD	2000	Yes		504	7.0		493	7.6		499	7.3
United States	OECD	2003	Yes		495	3.2		483	2.9		491	3.1
United States	OECD	2006	Yes					474	4.0		489	4.2
United States	OECD	2009	Yes		500	3.7		487	3.6		502	3.6
United States	OECD	2012	Yes		498	3.7		481	3.6		497	3.8
United States	OECD	2015	Yes		497	3.4		470	3.2		496	3.2
Uruguay	Partner	2000	No									
Uruguay	Partner	2003	No		434	3.4		422	3.3		438	2.9
Uruguay	Partner	2006	No		413	3.4		427	2.6		428	2.7
Uruguay	Partner	2009	No		426	2.6		427	2.6		427	2.6
Uruguay	Partner	2012	No		411	3.2		409	2.8		416	2.8
Uruguay	Partner	2015	No		437	2.5		418	2.5		435	2.2
Venezuela (Miranda)	Partner	2000	No									
Venezuela (Miranda)	Partner	2003	No									
Venezuela (Miranda)	Partner	2006	No									
Venezuela (Miranda)	Partner	2009	No		422	5.3		397	4.3		422	4.9
Venezuela (Miranda)	Partner	2012	No									
Venezuela (Miranda)	Partner	2015	No									
Viet Nam	Partner	2000	No									
Viet Nam	Partner	2003	No									
Viet Nam	Partner	2006	No									
Viet Nam	Partner	2009	No									
Viet Nam	Partner	2012	No		508	4.4		511	4.8		528	4.3
Viet Nam	Partner	2015	No		487	3.7		495	4.5		525	3.9
Yugoslavia	Partner	2000	No									
Yugoslavia	Partner	2003	No		412	3.6		437	3.8		436	3.5
Yugoslavia	Partner	2006	No									
Yugoslavia	Partner	2009	No									
Yugoslavia	Partner	2012	No									
Yugoslavia	Partner	2015	No									

Graphs by Country/Region
All countries/regions that
participated in all PISA
assessment cycles, OECD and
partners

Portugal

Reading Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in all PISA assessment cycles, OECD and partners

Mean value for Portugal

The red bar represent the 95 % confidence interval for the mean.

Mean value for each country/region

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.

The **red bar** represent the 95 % confidence interval for the mean.

The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions. The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Maximum value

Third quartile of the means (75 % of the means are below the third quartile)

Median of the means (50 % of the means are below the median)

First quartile of the means (25 % of the means are below the first quartile)

Minimum value

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

Portugal

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in all PISA assessment cycles, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region. The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean. The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions. The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentils of the means of the countries/regions.

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

Australia

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in all PISA assessment cycles, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region. The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean. The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions. The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

Belgium

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in all PISA assessment cycles, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region. The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean. The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions. The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

Brazil

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in all PISA assessment cycles, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.

The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean.

The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions. The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

Canada

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in all PISA assessment cycles, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region. The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean. The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions. The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

Czech Republic

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in all PISA assessment cycles, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.
The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean.
The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions.
The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

Denmark

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in all PISA assessment cycles, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region. The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean. The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions. The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

Finland

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in all PISA assessment cycles, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.

The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean.

The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions. The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

France

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in all PISA assessment cycles, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.
The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean.
The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions.
The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

Germany

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in all PISA assessment cycles, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region. The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean. The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions. The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

Greece

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in all PISA assessment cycles, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.
The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean.
The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions.
The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

Hong Kong (China)

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in all PISA assessment cycles, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.

The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean.

The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions. The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

Hungary

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in all PISA assessment cycles, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.
The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean.
The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions.
The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

Iceland

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in all PISA assessment cycles, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region. The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean. The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions. The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

Indonesia

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in all PISA assessment cycles, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region. The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean. The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions. The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

Ireland

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in all PISA assessment cycles, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.

The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean.

The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions. The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

Italy

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in all PISA assessment cycles, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region. The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean. The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions. The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentils of the means of the countries/regions.

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

Japan

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in all PISA assessment cycles, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region. The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean. The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions. The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

Korea

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in all PISA assessment cycles, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region. The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean. The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions. The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

Latvia

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in all PISA assessment cycles, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region. The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean. The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions. The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

Luxembourg

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in all PISA assessment cycles, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.

The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean.

The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions. The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

Mexico

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in all PISA assessment cycles, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.

The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean.

The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions. The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

New Zealand

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in all PISA assessment cycles, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region. The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean. The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions. The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

Norway

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in all PISA assessment cycles, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.

The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean.

The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions. The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

Poland

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in all PISA assessment cycles, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.

The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean.

The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions. The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

Russian Federation

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in all PISA assessment cycles, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region. The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean. The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions. The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

Spain

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in all PISA assessment cycles, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.

The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean.

The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions. The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

Sweden

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in all PISA assessment cycles, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region. The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean. The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions. The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

Switzerland

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in all PISA assessment cycles, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region. The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean. The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions. The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

Thailand

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in all PISA assessment cycles, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.
The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean.
The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions.
The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

USA

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in all PISA assessment cycles, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region. The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean. The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions. The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

Graphs by Country/Region
All countries/regions that
participated in at least one
assessment cycle, OECD
and partners

Albania

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.
 The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean.
 The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions.
 The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Algeria

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.
 The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean.
 The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions.
 The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Argentina

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.
 The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean.
 The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions.
 The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Austria

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.
 The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean.
 The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions.
 The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentils of the means of the countries/regions.

Azerbaijan

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.
 The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean.
 The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions.
 The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

B-S-J-G (China)

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.
 The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean.
 The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions.
 The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Bulgaria

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.
 The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean.
 The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions.
 The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

CABA (Argentina)

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.
 The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean.
 The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions.
 The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Chile

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region. The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean. The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions. The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Chinese Taipei

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.
 The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean.
 The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions.
 The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Colombia

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.
 The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean.
 The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions.
 The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Costa Rica

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.
 The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean.
 The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions.
 The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Croatia

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.
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 The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions.
 The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Cyprus

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.
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 The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions.
 The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Dominican Republic

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.
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 The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions.
 The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Dubai

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.
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 The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions.
 The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Estonia

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.
 The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean.
 The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions.
 The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentils of the means of the countries/regions.

FYROM (Macedonia)

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.
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 The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Georgia

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.
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 The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions.
 The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

India - Himachal Pradesh

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.
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 The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions.
 The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

India - Tamil Nadu

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.
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 The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions.
 The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Israel

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.
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 The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions.
 The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Jordan

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.
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 The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Kazakhstan

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.
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 The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions.
 The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Kosovo

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.
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 The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions.
 The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Kyrgyzstan

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.
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 The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions.
 The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentils of the means of the countries/regions.

Lebanon

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region. The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean. The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions. The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Liechtenstein

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.
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 The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions.
 The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Lithuania

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.
 The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean.
 The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions.
 The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Macao (China)

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.
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 The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions.
 The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Malaysia

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.
 The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean.
 The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions.
 The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Malta

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.
 The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean.
 The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions.
 The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Mauritius

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.
 The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean.
 The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions.
 The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Moldova

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.
 The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean.
 The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions.
 The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Montenegro

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.
 The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean.
 The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions.
 The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Netherlands

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region. The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean. The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions. The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Panama

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.
 The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean.
 The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions.
 The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Peru

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.
 The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean.
 The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions.
 The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.
 The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean.
 The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions.
 The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Romania

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region. The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean. The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions. The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Serbia

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.
 The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean.
 The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions.
 The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Shanghai (China)

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.
 The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean.
 The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions.
 The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Singapore

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.
 The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean.
 The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions.
 The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Slovak Republic

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.
 The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean.
 The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions.
 The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Slovenia

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.
 The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean.
 The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions.
 The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Trinidad and Tobago

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.
 The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean.
 The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions.
 The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Tunisia

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.
 The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean.
 The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions.
 The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Turkey

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.
 The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean.
 The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions.
 The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

United Arab Emirates

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.
 The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean.
 The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions.
 The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

United Kingdom

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.
 The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean.
 The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions.
 The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Uruguay

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.
 The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean.
 The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions.
 The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Venezuela (Miranda)

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.
 The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean.
 The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions.
 The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Viet Nam

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.
 The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean.
 The value, in *italic*, represent the median of the countries/regions.
 The box represents the 25th and the 75th percentiles of the means of the countries/regions.

Yugoslavia

Reading Literacy (Means)

Mathematical Literacy (Means)

Science Literacy (Means)

Compared with all countries/regions that participated in at least one assessment cycle, OECD and partners

The value, in **bold**, is the mean for the country/region.
 The **red bar** represent the 95% confidence interval for the mean.
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